

**LOW ENERGY SIMS CHARACTERIZATION OF PASSIVE OXIDE FILMS
FORMED ON A LOW-NICKEL STAINLESS STEEL IN ALKALINE MEDIA**

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Abstract

Low-energy secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) was used to study the oxide films formed on a low-nickel austenitic stainless steel (SS), potential replacement to conventional AISI 304 SS in reinforced concrete structures (RCS) that are subjected to aggressive environments. The effect of carbonation and the presence of chloride ions were studied.. The oxide films formed a chemically gradated bi-layer structure with an outer layer predominately constituted by iron oxides and an inner layer enriched in chromium oxides. Chloride ions were not found in the oxide film but did have an effect on film structure and thickness.

Key Words: SIMS; oxide film; low-nickel stainless steel; alkaline solution; depth profile.

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1. Introduction

Stainless steels (SS's) are alloys of great technological interest. The combination of good mechanical properties and exceptional resistance to corrosion establishes SS's as materials with a large number of industrial applications. Amongst their many applications, SS's have proved to be excellent structural materials in reinforced concrete structures (RCS) [1], even under highly aggressive conditions such as marine environments [2]. The SS's which have been used to date in RCS are mainly the austenitic grades AISI 304 and AISI 316. These austenitic grades combine ductility, strength and formability with the presence of a protective thin oxide film that forms on the surface of the alloy and acts as a physical barrier between the material and the environment, preventing the access of corrosive substances to the metal base, thus promoting a passive state. However, chloride ions can lead to de-passivation and premature failure of the structure due to corrosion when these ions reach the metal/concrete interface [2]. These aggressive agents may come from numerous sources such as sea-water spray or the sea itself when the structure protrudes into the sea (e.g. a pier, jetty or port), de-icing salts or contaminated sand used as aggregate in the composition of concrete [3].

Together with the presence of corrosive contaminants, such as chloride ions, the carbonation process represents another primary damage factor for RCS. Carbonation of concrete is a process by which carbon dioxide (CO_2) from the air penetrates into the concrete and reacts with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in the pores of concrete to form calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), leading to a decrease in the pH (~ 9), thus increasing the likelihood of active dissolution of the steel.

Among all the possible alternatives to these damaging factors in RCS working in highly aggressive environments, the use of SS reinforcements, and particularly the austenitic grades, appears to be a reliable way to guarantee the durability of RCS [4,5].

Nevertheless, its application has been limited because of the high initial costs involved in comparison with traditional carbon steel [2,6]. Nickel is one of the alloying elements that significantly increase the final price of austenitic SS. For this reason, new SS's in which the Ni content is partially replaced by other elements are being investigated with the aim of finding a cheaper but reliable alternative to traditional AISI 304 and AISI 316.

From the point of view of the study of the corrosion resistance of a passive metal or alloy such as a SS, the evaluation of its passive film is essential, as well as any differences that may occur in it under distinct external conditions. These oxide layers are typically of the order of 1–4 nm in thickness and their analysis is therefore challenging [7]. Secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) is a powerful surface characterization technique, which has sub–nanometre depth resolution and which offers the possibility of identifying chemical elements by allowing the detection of isotopes at very low concentration levels (ppm/ppb) [8]. Although the solid-state properties of passive films formed on SS have been widely studied using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Auger electron spectroscopy (AES) and X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) techniques [9-11], SIMS presents some advantages over these techniques such as a high surface specificity, greater than XPS and AES, and an elemental sensitivity of the order of ppm/ppb of a monolayer, whereas XPS and AES have sensitivities ~ 0.1 atomic percent [12]. SIMS also has the advantage of isotope specificity.

The aim of this paper is to investigate the combined effect of carbonation and the influence of chloride ions, both primary damaging factors on the corrosion of reinforcing materials in RCS, on the oxide film formed on a low-nickel SS using the SIMS technique. Evidence suggests that such environments are too aggressive for carbon steel to remain in a passive state, therefore the use of SS's may be an excellent alternative for extending the useful life service of RCS in such environments. A conventional AISI 304 SS was

also studied for comparative purposes as it is the traditional austenitic SS used as structural material in this type of construction. Special attention was paid to study the presence of any chloride ions in the passive film.

2. Experimental

The materials used in this work were low-nickel and AISI 304 SS plates provided by ACERINOX S. A. (Palmones, Cádiz, Spain). The samples were cut down to a size of 0.5 cm × 0.5 cm × 1 mm (Width × Length × Thickness). Table 1 shows the chemical composition (% by weight) of the two materials, according to the manufacturer. Specimens were initially polished using a series of silicon carbide (SiC) emery papers down to grade 1200 and subsequently polished using a diamond paste of 1 μm before finishing with an ultrasonic clean in ethanol for one minute and rinsed with distilled water.

The test solution was a carbonated solution with different concentrations of NaCl. A saturated Ca(OH)₂ solution with a pH~12–13 was prepared. Carbonation was achieved by bubbling CO₂ into the solution until a pH~8 was reached, a level below the referenced value of 9 to ensure the complete carbonation of the solution. The precipitated CaCO₃ formed was filtered and different amounts (0, 1.0, 3.0 and 5.0 %) of NaCl were added to the solution with the aim of evaluating the influence of chloride ion concentration in the film that forms on the surface of the material.

Specimens were immediately immersed in the solutions after the surface preparation. The total immersion time was 30 days. After this period the specimens were sequentially cleaned with isopropanol, ethanol and distilled water and dried in N₂ in order to remove any surface contamination before analysis.

An Atomika 4500 was used for the SIMS measurements. The conditions included a 500 eV Cs⁺ primary ion beam at 60° degrees from normal incidence. The beam current

was ~25 nA and the beam was rastered over an area of $600 \times 600 \mu\text{m}$.

3. Results and discussion

A SIMS depth profile for the low-nickel SS subjected to a carbonated solution with a NaCl content of 3.0% is shown in Fig. 1. This profile is representative of what was observed for both the low-nickel SS and AISI 304 SS for all NaCl concentrations tested. As observed, the $^{16}\text{O}^-$ signal indicates the extent of the oxide formed which is characterised by the onset of a leading edge after ~2-3 minutes and a trailing edge after ~9-10 minutes. Peaks in the chromium oxide signal ($^{68}\text{CrO}^-$) and the iron oxide signal ($^{72}\text{FeO}^-$) were also observed within this region. The $^{72}\text{FeO}^-$ peak intensity was detected closer to the surface of the oxide while the $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ peak intensity was deeper into the oxide (see inset in Fig. 1). This ion signal behaviour suggests that the layer formed on the SS surface is constituted by an oxide presenting a chemical gradient in composition which is formed of iron and chromium rich regions and which is stratified in structure. Thus, the signal detected for $^{16}\text{O}^-$ was due to the contribution from, at least, these two types of oxide.

The measured SIMS ion yields for different ion species are dependent on matrix effects and therefore are not necessarily proportional to the absolute concentration of the element analysed, so that their quantification is virtually impossible without known references [8]. Therefore, the differences in the signal intensities observed in the present work may well be due to these matrix effects (ion yield and sputter yield), uneven etching or charging. Since we are primarily interested in the relative variation in Fe and Cr oxides in the oxide all the peaks in the profiles presented have been interpreted based on normalised measurements unless the contrary is specified (as will be eventually detailed for data presented in Fig. 3). This way the signal intensity dependency was avoided. The

normalisation procedure consisted in the reassignment of the intensity values using the highest intensity value as a reference according to the following expression: $NI=I_t/I_{max}$ ($t=0, \dots, 30$ minutes); where NI represents the Normalised Intensity, I_t is the intensity registered in time from $t=0$ minutes (beginning of the test) to $t=30$ minutes (end of the test) and I_{max} is the highest intensity value in the profile. This procedure was carried out for each ion signal measured.

It is well known that, along with chemical composition of the surface oxide layer, its thickness is a parameter that plays a significant role in the corrosion resistance of a metal or a passive alloy [13]. For similar chemical composition, a thicker layer provides a more effective barrier against corrosive agents. Thus, thickness determination of the oxide films formed on the SS's studied is extremely informative.

Fig. 2 shows the normalised $^{16}O^-$ depth profiles for the low-nickel SS specimens subjected to the carbonated solution of different NaCl contents plotted as a function of time. Additionally, the $^{72}FeO^-$ and $^{68}CrO^-$ profiles are also represented because these oxides are believed to be the main constituents of the passive films formed (see Fig. 1). Attempts to represent the depth profiles as a function of depth were made, however the SIMS craters could not be clearly found after the tests as a result of the ultra-low energy used to perform the measurements. For this reason, all the profiles are presented as a function of the time of sputtering. As previously mentioned, the SIMS intensities measured are not necessarily proportional to the concentration of the element analysed. Nevertheless, as the oxide films were all observed to be of a similar chemical composition, to a first approximation the sputter yield was assumed to be likely constant for all the oxide films studied, so that a direct comparison between samples is thus valid [7]. In order to assess an approximate value for the determination of the time of sputtering required to remove the oxide layer formed on the surfaces, a reasonable benchmark of an

intensity decrease of the 90% with respect to the maxima observed in the $^{16}\text{O}^-$ signal, that is, the point where the $^{16}\text{O}^-$ signal was 0.1 with respect to the maximum intensity in the normalised profile (equal to unity), was considered as the point where the metal base was reached. This procedure, based on the assumption that sputtering rate of the oxide in the different samples is reasonable similar represents an approximation to the thickness of these passive films. Similar procedures have been used by other authors to determine the thickness of different passive films formed on iron by XPS [14]. In the absence of chlorides, it is observed that the metal/oxide layer interface was not reached within the time of sputtering performed, indicating that an extended sputtering process is required to assess this layer thickness. For the maximum NaCl concentrations used (3 % and 5.0 %), a sputtering time of 23.3 and 20.8 minutes were necessary to reach the metal base, respectively. These results indicate that the oxide layer thickness decreased with increased chloride ion content, thus leading to an expected reduction in the corrosion resistance of the low-nickel SS. The AISI 304 SS also showed a similar behaviour with the formation of thinner passive films for an increased NaCl concentration.

Fig. 3 shows Intensity Ratios (IR) for the $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ and $^{72}\text{FeO}^-$ signals taken from the low-nickel SS (Fig. 3a) and AISI 304 SS (Fig. 3b) subjected to the carbonated solution with different NaCl contents plotted as a function of time. IR's should allow the relative enrichment or depletion of one particular ionic species with respect to another to be determined. The relative intensity of these negative fragments has been calculated from the raw data using the following expression: $\text{IR} = \text{M} / ({}^{68}\text{CrO}^- + {}^{72}\text{FeO}^-)$, where M represents either the $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ or $^{72}\text{FeO}^-$ signals. Fig. 3a shows that for all NaCl concentrations, the relative intensity of $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ is lower than the $^{72}\text{FeO}^-$. In the first minutes of the profiles, the IR of the iron oxides increases to a maximum which coincides with a minimum in the relative intensity of the chromium oxides. However, as sputtering proceeds, a decrease in

the relative iron intensity is found while the chromium increases. After a certain depth of sputtering ($t \sim 10$ minutes), the profiles exhibit almost no variation, indicating the co-existence of both species in the oxide. An exception to this is observed for AISI 304 SS in the absence of chlorides, where the $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ maximum and $^{72}\text{FeO}^-$ minima coincide at $t \sim 15$ minutes. These results reaffirm the layered chemical nature of the oxide film formed in carbonated solution with different NaCl concentrations, whose inner layer is constituted by a chromium-rich oxide covered by an outer oxide layer rich in iron. In addition, the co-existence of the two chemical signals within the layer close to the oxide/metal interface, suggests that a mixed iron and chromium oxide constitutes the inner layer. It is important to realise, when looking at the shape of the profiles for the various elements, that the SIMS process introduced some perturbations due to ion beam mixing, uneven etching, matrix effects and so forth and that the observed signal is the convolution of the true signal and these SIMS induced artifacts.

Fig. 4 shows the normalised $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ depth profiles for low-nickel SS (Fig. 4a) and for AISI 304 SS (Fig. 4b) specimens in the carbonated solution with different NaCl contents plotted as a function of time. Fig. 4a shows that, in the absence of chlorides, a peak in the $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ signal at a depth corresponding to a sputtering time of $t \sim 6.5$ minutes is observed. When NaCl was introduced into the solution, the $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ peak appeared to shift towards the oxide/metal interface (the innermost region of the oxide layer) as the peak in signal occurs after a longer time in the corresponding profile ($t \sim 10$ to 12 minutes) (see in Fig. 4a). For the highest concentrations (3 % and 5 %) of NaCl the peak in the signal occurs at a similar sputtering time of $t \sim 10$ minutes while for a concentration of 1 % NaCl, a less well-defined peak is observed after $t \sim 12$ minutes of sputtering. These profiles suggest that the addition of NaCl modifies the surface chemistry in a concentration-dependent manner. As chromium in the oxide is largely attributed to be

responsible for the corrosion resistance, a decrease in the chromium-containing oxide thickness will lead to a less protective passive layer and thus, to a less corrosion resistant alloy. These results indicate that in the absence of chlorides, a certain chromium oxide thickness was achieved by the low-nickel SS subjected to the carbonated solution after the formation of the oxide layer due to the corresponding passivation process. However, upon increasing the NaCl concentration, the chromium oxide thickness was reduced as the $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ peaks observed appear further from the passive oxide surface, i.e. approaching the oxide/metal interface with a concurrent decrease in overall film thickness as indicated by the sputter time.

In the case of AISI 304 SS (Fig. 4b) an important difference is observed. Here, in the absence of chlorides a wide but well-defined peak in the $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ signal was found after $t\sim 16$ minutes of sputtering, but when the material was subjected to a solution that included NaCl of all the concentrations used, the peak in the $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ signal was observed at $t\sim 10$ minutes for all three samples. The influence of chlorides on the $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ profiles is in good qualitative agreement for both SS's in the presence of the higher NaCl content (3 % and 5 %), where the most aggressive conditions were considered. This way, although a similar behaviour is shown by the two studied SS's, subtle alloy dependent effects in response to the NaCl concentration is observed.

Fig. 5 shows normalised $^{72}\text{FeO}^-$ depth profiles for low-nickel SS (Fig. 5a) and for AISI 304 SS (Fig. 5b) specimens subjected to the carbonated solution with different NaCl contents plotted as a function of time. In Fig. 5a, specimens of low-nickel SS showed that in the absence of chlorides and up to a NaCl concentration equal to 1.0 %, a peak in the $^{72}\text{FeO}^-$ signal was observed for a similar sputtering time (depth), $t\sim 3$ minutes. For the higher NaCl concentrations tested (3 % and 5 %) the $^{72}\text{FeO}^-$ peak was shifted deeper towards the oxide/metal interface ($t\sim 5.4$ minutes), indicating a thinner layer of iron. A

lack of symmetry was observed in the $^{72}\text{FeO}^-$ peaks (see Fig. 5a), where the trailing edge of the signals presents a point of inflection or a second peak that coincided with the peaks of the $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ shown in Fig. 4a. This was more evident for the NaCl concentrations of 1% and 3%. According to these results and those observed in Fig. 3a, a contribution of iron oxides in the innerpart of the film, where the chromium oxides were detected, is observed; thus, confirming the coexistence of both species. Fig.5b shows that the AISI 304 SS exhibited a similar behavior to the low-nickel SS, although the $^{72}\text{FeO}^-$ peaks for AISI 304 were broader from Fig. 5a.

Fig. 6 shows the $^{74}\text{NiO}^-$ depth profile for low-nickel SS (Fig. 6a) and for AISI 304 SS (Fig. 6b) specimens in the carbonated solution with different NaCl contents plotted as a function of time. The ultimate sensitivity of a depth profiling analysis is determined by a signal to noise ratio (SNR). A very low SNR is exhibited for $^{74}\text{NiO}^-$ profile in both SS's. As observed in Fig. 1, the intensity signal registered for $^{74}\text{NiO}^-$ is very small and hard to detect even in the amplified profiles presented in the corresponding figure inset (see Fig. 1). The more plausible explanation to this behaviour might be due to a very low concentration of $^{74}\text{NiO}^-$ in the oxide layer, making the level of the intensity signal significantly smaller to the level of background noise.

Fig. 6a indicates that low-intensity oxidised nickel is detected within the innermost part of the oxide film which corresponds to the same position as that where the chromium oxides were observed (see Fig. 3a). However, upon closer inspection it is found that there is a slight shift in the peak maxima towards the oxide/metal interface for the $^{74}\text{NiO}^-$ compared to $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$. A slower dissolution and diffusion rate of nickel compared to iron and chromium, the main constituents of the passive films on SS's, may be responsible for the appearance of oxidised nickel at this position. Previous work has shown nickel to be present within the passive film for the low-nickel SS as evaluated in

this paper in saturated Ca(OH)_2 solution with different NaCl concentrations [15]. The presence of nickel in the oxide films formed on SS's could be attributed to the formation of nickel hydroxide as previously reported by Maurice *et al.* [16] for SS's and for nickel-based alloys containing chromium and iron. Addari *et al.* [17] also found oxidised nickel in the passive film of the AISI 304 SS that increased progressively with the time of immersion in a highly alkaline solution and that seemed to be proportional to the nickel bulk content. Fig 6b shows a similar behaviour. Peaks in the $^{74}\text{NiO}^-$ signal were observed in the AISI 304 SS at a sputtering time (depth) slightly higher than those observed for the chromium oxides, i.e. towards the metal/oxide interface. These results confirmed the presence of oxidised nickel in the passive film, despite chromium and iron being the main passivating species.

Finally, the possible incorporation of chlorides into the oxide layer formed on the surface of both SS's was studied. Chloride ions are well known for their ability to promote a localized attack on stainless steel in the form of pitting corrosion. Over the years theories for passive film breakdown and pit initiation have been categorized into three main mechanisms that focus on passive film penetration, film breaking, or adsorption [18]. Hence, the study on the interaction of these ions with the passive films formed on the studied materials is necessary to eventually understand their corrosion behaviour in chloride containing media. Additionally, the evaluation of whether these ions incorporate into the passive film is highly interesting because their presence within such oxides is somewhat controversial. Previous studies did *not* find any participation of these ions in an alkaline solution containing NaCl in different concentrations [15], and therefore suggested that the chloride ions do not incorporate into the passive film, but are detected as a result of an adsorption process on the alloy surface. However, other authors have observed different results [19-21]. The more plausible explanation about the detection of

chloride ions in the oxide formed on the SS surface is that suggesting that chloride ions present in the electrolyte are *incorporated* into the passive film whereby they can occupy the positions of oxygen ions. Nevertheless, these contradictory results are most likely due to differences in the sample preparation. In those studies in which chlorides were found to be part of the passive film, this was electrochemically formed by different anodic potential applications, while in the present and a previous research work [15] the oxide film was formed by immersion in the test solution at the corrosion potential (E_{corr}). The cause of choosing this experimental procedure was to approach as much as possible the real conditions of a reinforcing structure during its life in service. In either case, it is clear that chlorides play a role in the oxide formation on SS because a threshold was found above which the relative amount of chromium and iron decreased, resulting in an oxide layer less protective against the corrosion processes [15]. Fig. 7 shows the $^{35}\text{Cl}^-$ depth profile for low-nickel SS (Fig. 7a) and for AISI 304 SS (Fig. 7b) specimens subjected to the carbonated solution with different NaCl contents plotted as a function of time. As observed in Fig. 7a, a single $^{35}\text{Cl}^-$ peak was detected for the low-nickel SS specimen in the absence of chloride ions and was located at the outermost part of the oxide film ($t \sim 0.5$ minutes). The appearance of this peak is attributed to the adsorption of chlorides on the SS surface during the preparation and/or handling of the sample before its insertion into the SIMS instrument. It should be noted that the lack of chloride ions in the carbonated solution prevents it from being the source of contamination. In the presence of NaCl, a coinciding peak was found for the low-nickel SS for all NaCl concentrations tested. AISI 304 SS behaved in a similar way to the low-nickel SS (see Fig. 7b). The similarity in the peak position in the absence and presence of NaCl suggests that chlorides are not incorporated into the oxide film structure and are detected as a result of prior adsorption processes on the SS surface.

4. Conclusions

Low-energy SIMS spectra indicated a stratified structure in the passive film presenting a chemical gradient, whose inner layer was a chromium-rich oxide covered by an outer layer of iron-rich oxide. Iron oxide was also found in the inner oxide as well as small amount of oxidised nickel at the oxide/metal interface. Finally, chloride ions were not found in the inner passive regions of the oxide film structure formed on the surfaces of low-nickel and AISI 304 SS. Preparation of the sample in terms of oxide film generation method appears to have a direct relation with the possible presence of these ions in the film. However, chlorides did show an influence in the passive film growth, promoting thinner passive layers with the increase in the NaCl concentration.

The low-nickel SS presented in this paper shows very similar oxide layer chemical composition and distribution of species to conventional austenitic AISI 304 SS. If further experimental results obtained by electrochemical means confirm a similar corrosion resistance in carbonated media containing NaCl, this new alloy may be a viable material to be used as the reinforcement in RCS in aggressive environments.

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References

- [1] N.R. Baddoo, Stainless steel in construction: A review of research, applications, challenges and opportunities, *J. Constr. Steel Res.* 64 (2008) 1199-1206.
- [2] S. Fajardo, D.M. Bastidas, M. Criado, M. Romero, J.M. Bastidas, Corrosion behavior of a new low-nickel stainless steel in saturated calcium hydroxide solution, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 25(2011) 4190-4196.
- [3] M.A.G. Tommaselli, N.A. Mariano, S.E. Kuri, Effectiveness of corrosion inhibitors in saturated calcium hydroxide solutions acidified by acid rain components, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 23 (2009) 328-33.
- [4] M.B. Valcarce, M. Vázquez, Carbon steel passivity examined in alkaline solutions: The effect of chloride and nitrite ions, *Electrochim. Acta* 53 (2008) 5007–5015.
- [5] Z.Q. Tan, C.M. Hansson, Effect of surface condition on the initial corrosion of galvanized reinforcing steel embedded in concrete, *Corros. Sci.* 50(2008) 2512–2522.
- [6] M. Criado, D.M. Bastidas, S. Fajardo, A. Fernández-Jiménez, J.M. Bastidas, Corrosion behavior of a new low-nickel stainless steel embedded in activated fly ash mortars, *Cem. Concr. Compos.* 33(2011) 644-652.
- [7] E.E. Rees, D.S. McPhail, M.P. Ryan, J. Kelly, M.G. Dowsett, Low energy SIMS characterization of ultra thin oxides on ferrous alloys, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 203-204 (2003) 660-664.
- [8] D.S. McPhail, Applications of secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) in materials science, *J. Mater. Sci.* 41 (2006) 873-903.
- [9] L. Wegrelius, F. Falkenberg, I. Olefjord, Passivation of Stainless Steels in

- Hydrochloric Acid, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 146 (1999) 1397–1406.
- [10] G. Lothongkum, S. Chaikittisilp, A.W. Lothongkum, XPS investigation of surface films on high Cr-Ni ferritic and austenitic stainless steels, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 218 (2003) 203–210.
- [11] J.M. Bastidas, C.L. Torres, E. Cano, J.L. Polo, Influence of molybdenum on passivation of polarised stainless steels in a chloride environment, *Corros. Sci.* 44 (2002) 625–633.
- [12] Annick Hubin, Herman Terryn, Chapter 6 X-ray photoelectron and Auger electron spectroscopy, In: K. Janssens and R. Van Grieken, Editor(s), *Comprehensive Analytical Chemistry*, Elsevier, 2004, Volume 42, Pages 277-312.
- [13] Chun-Che Shih, Chun-Ming Shih, Yea-Yang Su, Lin Hui Julie Su, Mau-Song Chang, Shing-Jong Lin, Effect of surface oxide properties on corrosion resistance of 316L stainless steel for biomedical applications, *Corros. Sci.* 46 (2004) 427-441.
- [14] I.V. Sieber, H. Hildebrand, S. Virtanen, P. Schmuki, Investigations on the passivity of iron in borate and phosphate buffers, pH 8.4, *Corrosion Science* 48 (2006) 3472–3488.
- [15] S. Fajardo, D.M Bastidas, M.P. Ryan, M. Criado, D.S. McPhail, J.M. Bastidas, Low-nickel stainless steel passive film in simulated concrete pore solution: A SIMS study, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 256 (2010) 6139-6143.
- [16] V. Maurice, W.P. Yang, P. Marcus, X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy and Scanning Tunnelling Microscopy study of passive films formed on (100) Fe-18Cr-13Ni single crystal surfaces, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 145 (1998) 909-920.
- [17] D.Addari, B. Elsener, A. Rossi, Electrochemistry and surface chemistry of stainless steels in alkaline media simulating concrete pore solutions, *Electrochim.*

Acta 53 (2008) 8078-8086.

- [18] Strehblow, H. H., Mechanisms of pitting corrosion. In Corrosion Mechanisms in Theory and Practice, 2nd edn, Marcus, P. (ed.), Marcel Dekker: New York, (2002).
- [19] S. Mischler, A. Vogel, H.J. Mathieu, D. Landolt, The chemical composition of the passive film on Fe-24Cr and Fe-24Cr-11Mo studied by AES, XPS and SIMS, Corros. Sci.32 (1991) 925-944.
- [20] I. Olefjord, L. Wegrelius, Surface Analysis of Passive State, Corros Sci, 31 (1990) 89-98.
- [21] V. Mitrovic-Scepanovic, B. MacDougall, M.J. Graham, Nature of Passive Films on Fe-26Cr Alloy, Corros Sci, 24 (1984) 479-490.

Fig. 1 Depth profile for low-nickel SS immersed in carbonated solution with a NaCl content of 3.0%. Cs^+ primary beam, 500 eV, 25 nA. Crater size of 600 μm .

Fig. 2 Normalised depth profiles for low-nickel SS specimens immersed in carbonated solution with different concentrations of NaCl, showing $^{16}\text{O}^-$, $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ and $^{72}\text{FeO}^-$ content of the oxide layer. Cs^+ primary beam, 500 eV, 25 nA. Crater size of 600 μm .

Fig. 3 Intensity ratio profiles for negative species $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ and $^{72}\text{FeO}^-$ on the (a) low-nickel SS, and (b) AISI 304 SS in carbonated solution with different NaCl contents: $^{68}\text{CrO}^- / (^{68}\text{CrO}^- + ^{72}\text{FeO}^-)$ and $^{72}\text{FeO}^- / (^{68}\text{CrO}^- + ^{72}\text{FeO}^-)$.

Fig. 4 Normalised depth profiles for (a) low-nickel SS, and (b) AISI 304 SS specimens immersed in carbonated solution with different concentrations of NaCl, showing $^{68}\text{CrO}^-$ content of the oxide layer. Cs^+ primary beam, 500 eV, 25 nA. Crater size of 600 μm .

Fig. 5 Normalised depth profiles for (a) low-nickel SS, and (b) AISI SS specimens immersed in carbonated solution with different concentrations of NaCl, showing $^{72}\text{FeO}^-$ content of the oxide layer. Cs^+ primary beam, 500 eV, 25 nA. Crater size of 600 μm .

Fig. 6 Normalised depth profiles for (a) low-nickel SS, and (b) AISI SS specimens immersed in carbonated solution with different concentrations of NaCl, showing $^{74}\text{NiO}^-$ content of the oxide layer. Cs^+ primary beam, 500 eV, 25 nA. Crater size of 600 μm .

Fig. 7 Normalised depth profiles for (a) low-nickel SS, and (b) AISI SS specimens immersed in carbonated solution with different concentrations of NaCl, showing $^{35}\text{Cl}^-$ content of the oxide layer. Cs^+ primary beam, 500 eV, 25 nA. Crater size of 600 μm .

